

**Reliability and validity evidence of the Expressive and Instrumental
Aggression Questionnaire (CAIE) in prison inmates**

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Abstract

The Instrumental and Expressive Aggression Questionnaire (CAIE) is a self-report instrument that allows evaluating aggression based on its motivational bases. The objective of this study was to evaluate its psychometric properties in a Spanish prison sample. The CAIE and other scales (SAQ, PCL-R, and VRAG) were completed by 302 male offenders from several Spanish prisons. The confirmatory factor analysis showed that the structure of the CAIE was explained by a three-factor solution (two first-order factors and one second-order factor). The Cronbach's alpha and omega coefficients showed adequate internal consistency of the total CAIE score and its subscales. In addition, the correlations obtained between the CAIE and the other scales were statistically significant and showed high and moderate magnitudes, indicating evidence of concurrent validity of the instrument. The results indicate the importance of aggression as a factor to be taken into account when assessing the risk of violence.

Introduction

The increase in aggressive behaviors in recent years has caused aggression to be considered a major social problem worldwide (Azevedo et al., 2018; De Boer, 2018; Fanning, et al., 2019; Fraga, 2016). Consequently, in 2014, the World Health Organization (WHO, 2014), the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC), and the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) launched the report on the world situation of violence prevention. In this report, they estimated that 475,000 people worldwide were victims of homicide (6.7 per 100,000 inhabitants), mainly men between 15-44 years of age, and considering this as the third leading cause of death among men in this age group. Finally, other research on this area (Horcajo et al., 2019; Lam et al., 2021; Lee, 2016) also shows the current importance of the

development of studies on violence, as we not only find ourselves in a historical moment for its prevention but also such studies are a part of the international health agenda.

Aggression can be understood as the behavior that is directed at another individual with the immediate intention of causing harm, that is, the aggressor believes that they will harm the other individual, who will be motivated to evade the attack (Anderson & Bushman, 2002; Stanford et al., 2003). Human aggression, according to its different motivations, has been classified in two different dimensions: instrumental aggression and expressive aggression (Cima et al., 2013; Ramírez, 2013; Ramírez & Andreu, 2003). Instrumental aggression is a planned, deliberate, and conscious behavior, in which there is a desire to harm to achieve a certain end (Meloy, 2006; Raine et al., 2006). Expressive aggression is characterized by uncontrolled and exaggerated behaviors caused by intense negative emotions or by the biased assessment of the stimulus that caused them (Barrat et al., 1999; Cima & Raine, 2009; Houston et al., 2003). Both types of aggression refer to the motivations and degree of control that the person has over their aggressive reactions to certain contexts, offering a functional point of view of the evaluation and intervention in aggressive behavior in different areas (Andreu & Peña, 2019; Matlasz et al., 2020; Meyer et al., 2016; Swogger et al., 2015).

It must be considered that the prison context is characterized by a high prevalence of aggressive behaviors (Azevedo et al., 2020; James et al., 2020), and therefore, it is of great importance to have validated instruments in this population to assess aggression, its prevalence and typologies to improve and guarantee greater effectiveness in intervention strategies (Azevedo et al., 2018; Kuyck et al., 2013). In addition, it is relevant to distinguish between the two types of aggression when evaluating the risk of violence, taking into account their influence in the prediction of subsequent crimes (Ennis et al., 2017; Martin et al., 2019; Matlasz et al., 2020; Rouchy et al., 2019; Swogger et al., 2015; Zabala-Baños et al., 2019).

On another hand, the distinction between instrumental and expressive aggression has also been considered in the assessment of offenders to determine the different types of aggressors and be able to treat them in a more individualized way (Alonso et al., 2022; Ennis et al., 2017; Greenall & Wright, 2020; Liu et al., 2021).

Unfortunately, there are few instruments to evaluate aggression in samples of adult offenders, especially the types of aggression based on their motivational bases. In this regard, there are two instruments mainly aimed at evaluating aggressive behavior that consider this categorization: the Impulsive-Premeditated Aggression Scale (IPAS; Stanford et al., 2003) and the Reactive-Proactive Aggression Questionnaire (RPQ; Raine et al., 2006). These questionnaires present good psychometric properties; specifically, the internal consistency of the IPAS (Stanford et al., 2003) was measured in North American samples with Cronbach's alpha, obtaining adequate levels of reliability both for the Impulsive scale (.77) and the Premeditated scale (.82). Similarly, good levels of reliability were also obtained in the measure of the Reactive and Proactive Aggression Questionnaire in adolescent boys, with a Cronbach's alpha of .90 for the total scale, .84 for the Reactive scale, and .86 for the Proactive scale. However, these scales are insufficient to evaluate this type of aggression in the adult population in prison contexts.

Consequently, the absence of specific psychometric assessment instruments in the adult population, and especially in forensic and prison contexts, makes it necessary to create and develop other instruments such as the Instrumental and Expressive Aggression Questionnaire (CAIE; Andreu & Peña, 2019), which assesses aggression based on its characteristic motivational bases. The CAIE is a simple instrument that can be administered individually or collectively in adults between 18 and 65 years of age, and it can also be applied as a self-report technique for the psychological evaluation of aggressive behavior in the general community population. It can be also used as a complementary test in clinical

psychological evaluation processes of adults suffering from psychopathological conditions where aggressive behavior is an important factor to consider (for example, antisocial or borderline personality disorder, psychopathy, or impulse control disorders). It is also useful in forensic psychological assessment processes to measure the risk of violence in the forensic and penitentiary population (Andreu et al., 2020; Gómez, 2009).

On another hand, the use of assessment instruments that distinguish between the two types of aggression in forensic contexts would allow us to complement the assessment of the degree of control and motivation of aggressive behavior. This would provide useful evidence to assess the volitional capacity and self-control of the person under evaluation, and also the risk factors present in the management of violence (Andreu & Peña, 2019; James et al., 2020; Swogger et al., 2015).

Therefore, taking into account the lack of instruments for assessing aggression in adults in forensic and prison contexts, the objective of this study was to analyse the CAIE questionnaire in a sample of Spanish criminals to provide more empirical evidence on the factorial validity of the instrument, as well as to determine its internal consistency and concurrent and predictive validity with other instruments for assessing the risk of violence.

Method

Participants

Three hundred and two male offenders who were incarcerated in various prisons in the Community of Madrid (Spain) participated in the present study. The average age of the participants was 35.33 years ($SD = 10.24$, ranging from 20 to 67 years). Of them, 73.8% were Spanish, and 26.2% were of other nationalities. Table 1 displays the demographic characteristics of the offenders. The most typical crimes for which they were currently in prison are: injuries or assaults (49.7%), robberies with violence and intimidation (30.8%) and family violence (22.5%). See Table 2 for the criminal characteristics of the offenders.

INSERT **TABLE 1** APPROXIMATELY HERE

INSERT **TABLE 2** APPROXIMATELY HERE

Instruments

To carry out this study in the prison population, some instruments, listed below, were selected that have consistently shown high validity and reliability in assessing the risk of violence, have been previously adapted to the Spanish prison population, and have a low cost in terms of application time.

The *Instrumental and Expressive Aggression Questionnaire* (CAIE; Andreu & Peña, 2019) is a self-report instrument designed to assess aggression through two dimensions: the Instrumental Scale assesses deliberate, conscious and planned aggression, and the Expressive Scale assesses reactive and unplanned aggression, produced in the absence of control. The instrument shows high levels of reliability with a Cronbach's alpha of .88 for the Instrumental scale, .87 for the Expressive scale, and .93 for the total scale.

The *Self-Appraisal Questionnaire* (SAQ; Loza, 2005). The SAQ is a self-report instrument designed to predict violent and nonviolent recidivism and assess treatment needs in a correctional and forensic population. The questionnaire consists of 72 true-false items that comprise 8 subscales: Criminal Tendencies, Antisocial Personality, Conduct Problems, Criminal History, Alcohol and Drug Use, Antisocial Associates, Anger and Validity. Only the first six of these eight subscales, composed of 67 items, are used for the prediction of recidivism. The Spanish version of the SAQ (Andreu et al., 2015) was used in the present study. It showed an adequate level of reliability, and internal consistency for the total score

and subscales: the alpha coefficient for the total score was .92, and the alpha coefficients for the subscales ranged from .35 to .83.

The *Psychopathy Checklist-Revised* (PCL-R; Hare, 2003). The PCL-R consists of 20 items and 2 factors assessing psychopathy in clinical and forensic populations. Several studies have supported the psychometric properties of the PCL-R as well as its use as a predictor of violence (Denomme et al., 2020; Horcajo-Gil et al., 2019; Olver et al., 2020). The PCL-R is scored using a 0-, 1- or 2-point scale, and the total score can range from 0 to 40 points. Scores higher than 30 identify the person as a primary psychopath, whereas the presence of psychopathy traits is reflected in scores between 20 and 29 points. The Spanish standardization of the PCL-R (Moltó et al., 2010) was used in the present study. This instrument showed adequate internal consistency and high reliability, with a Cronbach's alpha of .85 and a mean inter-item correlation of .22.

The *Violence Risk Appraisal Guide* (VRAG; Harris et al., 1993). The VRAG is a measure developed for assessing the risk of violent recidivism in mental patients and penitentiary and forensic populations. The instrument displays an offender's likelihood of committing another violent crime. Higher scores indicate a greater risk of reoffending violently. The instrument consists of a list of 12 items: living with parents at 16 age, elementary school maladjustment, history of alcohol problems, marital status, history of nonviolent offenses, prior parole failure, age at index offense, injuries inflicted, any female victim for index offense, presence of personality disorder, diagnosis of schizophrenia, and PCL-R score. The Spanish version of the VRAG (Ballesteros et al., 2006) was used in the present study. It showed an adequate level of reliability: the alpha coefficient for the total score was .90 and alpha coefficients for the subscales ranged from .56 to .85.

Procedure

Participation in the present study was voluntary, and the following inclusion criteria were used: speaking Spanish, basic level of literacy, and having given written informed consent to participate in the research. All participants were informed that the information provided would be used for research purposes and that all their data would remain confidential. They were individually interviewed and assessed with the aforementioned psychometric measures. Offenders' criminal history was obtained from penitentiary files.

Statistical and psychometric analysis

To test the factorial structure of the CAIE, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was applied using the AMOS program. The present study used multiple statistical tests and indexes designed to assess the goodness of fit of the data to the proposed models, following the recommendations of Hu and Bentler (1999). In the case of the goodness of fit index (GFI), values greater than .95 indicated a good fit. Adjusted goodness of fit index (AGFI) values greater than .90 indicated a good fit. Normed fit index (NFI) values greater than or equal to .90 indicated acceptable model fit, and values lower than .90 can usually be improved substantially.

Internal consistency of the CAIE was examined with Cronbach's alpha and the Omega coefficient. Pearson correlations were used to analyze the concurrent validity of the CAIE with related variables of risk of recidivism. Group differences comparing variables such as institutional and non-institutional infractions were analyzed using Student's *t*-test, determining the effect size with partial eta squared coefficient (η_p^2). η_p^2 values around .01 indicate a small effect size, around .06 a medium effect size, and equal to or greater than .14 a large effect size. To examine the CAIE's predictive efficiency for the risk of recidivism, the ROC curve was taken into account. For this purpose, the sample was divided into two groups (recidivist offenders and non-recidivist offenders) based on the score obtained on the SAQ

instrument. The group of non-recidivists was made up of the inmates who obtained scores between 0 and 18 on this instrument, while the group of recidivists was made up of inmates whose scores ranged between 19 and 55 points. All analyses were performed with the SPSS software (v. 25.0).

Results

Factor-Analytic validity

Confirmatory factor analysis using the Unweighted Least Square (ULS) estimation method showed that CAIE subscales fit a model of 22 items grouped into two first-order factors integrated (instrumental aggression and expressive aggression) by a general second-order factor (general aggression factor). These results showed a good fit of the model (GFI = .95, AGFI = .94, NFI = .94). The squared multiple correlations (R^2) ranged from .19 to .62, and the factor loadings from .44 to .79 (see Table 3).

INSERT **TABLE 3** APPROXIMATELY HERE

Internal consistency analysis

Table 4 shows the alpha and omega coefficients for the CAIE total score and subscales: Instrumental and Expressive scales. The alpha and omega coefficients for the CAIE total score were .92 and .93, respectively, and the alpha and omega coefficients for the subscales were .86 for the Instrumental scale and .89 and .90 for the Expressive scale.

INSERT **TABLE 4** APPROXIMATELY HERE

Concurrent validity

Concurrent validity was estimated by correlating CAIE scores with three instruments that assess risk of recidivism. Pearson correlation coefficients are shown in Table 5. The CAIE

total score showed moderate correlations with the PCL-R total score ($r = .48, p < .01$) and VRAG total score ($r = .42, p < .01$), and higher correlations with the SAQ total score ($r = .53, p < .01$). Correlations between the Instrumental scale and the PCL-R, VRAG, and SAQ total scores were moderate ($r = .46, p < .01; r = .38, p < .01; r = .44, p < .01$). Additionally, the Expressive scale score showed moderate correlations with the PCL-R and VRAG total scores ($r = .46, p < .01; r = .39, p < .01$), and higher correlations with the SAQ total score ($r = .55, p < .01$). The correlations between the subscales of the CAIE and Factor 1 of the PCL-R were weak, whereas the analysis of the correlations between the Instrumental scale and Factor 2 of the PCL-R showed a moderate correlation ($r = .47, p < .01$), and a higher correlation with the Expressive scale ($r = .51, p < .01$). Lastly, the CAIE total score had a higher correlation with PCL-R Factor 2 ($r = .53$) than Factor 1 ($r = .28$).

INSERT TABLE 5 APPROXIMATELY HERE

Differences between institutional and non-institutional infractions

In the analysis of the differences between both groups, the infraction group included participants who had committed at least one institutional infraction, and the non-infraction group had no infractions. These groups were compared on the CAIE total and subscale scores. The results showed that the means for the infraction group were always higher than the means of the non-infraction group, and the differences were statistically significant in all measures (see Table 6).

INSERT TABLE 6 APPROXIMATELY HERE

Predictive validity

The next step in the examination of the validity of the CAIE was through the investigation of its predictive efficiency. For this purpose, we used the Receiving Operator Characteristic (ROC) curve and the Area Under the Curve (AUC). The AUC values estimated using the ROC statistic can range between 0.0 (lack of predictive validity) to 1.0 (perfect predictive validity). Values above .556 are considered low, .639 moderate and .714 high (Rice & Harris, 2005).

The ROC analysis carried out on the CAIE total score revealed an AUC of .77 (95% CI [0.72, 0.83]), on the Instrumental scale, it revealed an AUC of .79 (95% CI [0.74, 0.84]), and on the Expressive scale, it revealed an AUC of .73 (95% CI [0.66, 0.79]). This result shows an acceptable accuracy discriminating between low risk of recidivism and moderate/high risk of recidivism, especially on the Instrumental scale. Figure 1 presents the ROC curve for CAIE total score, subscales, and recidivism.

INSERT FIGURE 1 APPROXIMATELY HERE

Figure 2 presents the ROC curves comparing the predictive efficiency of the CAIE total score, the CAIE subscales, the PCL-R total score, the PCL-R Factor 1, and the PCL-R Factor 2 for recidivism. The highest AUC of the CAIE was obtained by the Instrumental scale (.79), followed by the CAIE total score (.77) and the Expressive scale (.73). The general highest AUC was obtained by PCL-R Factor 2 (AUC = .88), and the AUC of the PCL-R total score (.83). The lowest AUC was obtained by PCL-R Factor 1 (.69).

INSERT FIGURE 2 APPROXIMATELY HERE

Discussion

The main objective of this study was to analyse the psychometric properties of the CAIE instrument in a Spanish prison sample. For this purpose, its factorial structure, internal consistency, concurrent validity, and predictive capacity were determined. In general terms, the CAIE analysis showed adequate levels of reliability and validity. Regarding the study of its factorial structure, the CFA indicated the appropriate fit of the three-factor model composed of two first-order factors that encompass the two subscales that make up the instrument (Instrumental and Expressive) and a second-order factor that refers to general aggression. In addition, the factor loadings of all the items were satisfactory, and the fit indexes can be considered satisfactory.

Regarding the general internal consistency of the total CAIE score, it was high, as was that of the Instrumental and Expressive subscales. These results are very similar to those obtained in psychometric validation studies of other instruments also aimed at evaluating instrumental and expressive aggression, such as the RPQ (Andreu et al., 2009; Dinić et al., 2020; Raine et al., 2006) or the IPAS (Azevedo et al., 2018; López, 2015). Although our values are adequate, more studies are recommended to help determine the temporal reliability of the instrument.

For the analysis of concurrent validity, the CAIE was compared with instruments that assess the risk of recidivism such as the SAQ (Loza, 2005), the PCL-R (Hare, 2003), and the VRAG (Harris et al., 1993). In the present study, the total score of the CAIE showed high correlations with the SAQ and moderate ones with the VRAG and the PCL-R, and this correlation was high with Factor 2 of the PCL-R. The Expressive scale showed a higher correlation with the SAQ than the Instrumental scale, while both scales showed a moderate correlation with the VRAG and the PCL-R. Along these same lines, and specifically related to Factor 2 of the PCL-R, the Expressive scale showed a high correlation, while the correlation

between this factor and the Instrumental scale was moderate. These results, in accordance with previous studies (Ennis et al., 2017; Martin et al., 2019; Matlasz et al., 2020; Rouchy et al., 2019; Swogger et al., 2015; Zabala-Baños et al., 2019), indicate that aggression is an important factor to consider when predicting the risk of recidivism, mainly the presence of expressive aggression, and therefore, the CAIE is a useful instrument in evaluations of this type.

Following the studies that have taken into account the distinction between instrumental and expressive aggression when evaluating the delinquent population (Alonso et al., 2022; Ennis et al., 2017; Greenall & Wright, 2020; Liu et al., 2021), in our study, it is shown that institutional offenders obtained higher scores in the total CAIE and both subscales (Instrumental and Expressive) compared to institutional non-offenders. Specifically, and taking only the subscales of the instrument into account, both groups showed a more typically expressive aggression. Therefore, these results suggest that high scores on the CAIE and its subscales reflect a high probability of committing offenses in prison and a greater predisposition to breaching the rules.

Regarding the predictive efficiency of the instrument, it was analysed using the ROC curve to determine the discrimination capacity of the CAIE between reoffenders and non-reoffenders. The three scales that make up the instrument obtained AUC values between .73 and .79, which indicates a moderate discrimination capacity of the tool. The Instrumental scale obtained a higher AUC score (.79), and therefore, it showed the greatest predictive capacity between reoffenders and non-reoffenders. Finally, a comparative ROC curve was carried out between the CAIE and the PCL-R, considering the PCL-R as a reference instrument for assessing the risk of recidivism in samples of offenders (Andrés-Pueyo & Echeburúa, 2010). The results showed a greater discriminative capacity by PCL-R Factor 2

(.88) and the total score of the PCL-R (.83), followed by the Instrumental scale (.79) and the total CAIE score (.77).

Therefore, the results of our study show that the CAIE is a reliable and valid instrument as a complementary tool for the evaluation of the risk of recidivism, which will add new information to the evaluation and management of risk. Obtaining information on the level and type of aggression will not only provide more indications to the assessment of the risk of recidivism but will also allow a greater individualization of the subsequent intervention. In this way, the use of the CAIE is recommended in assessments related to the risk of recidivism together with other validated instruments to achieve this specific objective. However, it is necessary to take into account a limitation of this study, that is, the retrospective design used that does not allow a prediction of recurrence after a follow-up period.

To sum up, the development of an instrument such as the CAIE to assess expressive and instrumental aggression in an adult prison population is not only a relevant scientific contribution, given the lack of psychometric instruments that assess both types of aggression based on motivational dimensions of aggression, but also, according the results of our study on its validity, as a complementary tool in the assessment of delinquents with a high risk of violence.

Disclosure statement

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

Data availability statement

The data used in the research is private and cannot be shared.

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Table 1. Sample Sociodemographic Characteristics (N = 302)

	Frequency	%
<i>Marital status</i>		
Single	137	45.4
Married	38	12.6
Divorced/separated	64	21.2
Couple	5	1.7
Dk/Da	58	19.1
<i>Education</i>		
No studies	4	1.3
Primary education	165	54.6
Secondary education	76	25.2
Post-secondary non-tertiary education	23	7.6
Tertiary education	27	8.9
Dk/Da	7	2.4
<i>Professional status</i>		
Unemployed	89	29.5
Unqualified employee	92	30.5
Qualified employee	84	27.8
Entrepreneur	17	5.6
Employee with higher education	13	4.3
Dk/Da	7	2.3

Note. Dk/Da = Didn't know/didn't answer

Table 2. Criminal Characteristics of the Sample (N = 302)

	Values
Current sentence length (months)	2-588
<i>M</i>	109.80
<i>SD</i>	130.60
Age at current incarceration (years)	31.12
<i>SD</i>	9.19
Minimum and maximum values	18 - 62
Average number of previous prison admissions (with or without conviction)	2.37
<i>SD</i>	2.49
Minimum and maximum values	1 - 15
Age at first incarceration (years)	27.56
<i>SD</i>	9.21
Minimum and maximum values	16 - 66

Table 3. Scale Items and Psychometric Properties of the CAIE Dimensions

	<i>Factor loading</i>	<i>R²</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
<i>Instrumental Scale</i>				
2. When I attack someone, I tend to think that it is justified	.774*	.599	1.4 9	1.51
4. I think being aggressive is necessary to get what you want	.484*	.235	0.8 4	1.26
7. I have wished that some of the aggeesions that I finally committed would happen	.490*	.240	0.6 9	1.12
8. I think the person I attacked really deserced it	.718*	.515	1.6 3	1.61
9. Being aggressive has allowed me to have power over others and improve my self-esteem	.552*	.305	0.8 0	1.27
10. I know most of the people I have assaulted	.607*	.369	1.3 0	1.48
11. I believe that some of the aggressions I committed were for revenge	.592*	.351	1.0 0	1.42
12. I knew I was going to get angry before I attacked someone	.721*	.520	1.4 4	1.63
13. My anger is usually directed at a specific person	.441*	.194	1.3 5	1.51
14. Assaulting someone is a relief, so I usually feel better after doing it	.560*	.314	0.4 6	0.92
15. On some opportunities I have been glad to have reacted aggressively	.569*	.324	0.6 1	1.18
<i>Expressive Scale</i>				
3. I often don't remember details well after reacting aggressively	.621*	.386	1.1 3	1.44
4. I feel that when I attack another person, I tend to lose control of myself	.689*	.475	1.4 9	1.59
6. I think I have lost control in some discussion	.742*	.550	1.7 8	1.73
7. Before being aggressive with someone, I get very nervous or upset	.693*	.481	1.8 6	1.67
9. I am often concerned about my safety when I react aggressively	.554*	.307	1.8 0	1.78

10. I think that during the last few months I have been more aggressive than usual	.490*	.240	0.4 4	0.91
11. During an assault, I often feel confused	.479*	.230	1.2 8	1.49
12. I think my behavior was excessive and disproportionate to the provocation	.725*	.525	1.0 6	1.34
13. I think my aggressive reactions are often uncontrolled	.756*	.572	1.5 4	1.59
14. When I behave aggressively, I tend to be in bad mood	.734*	.539	1.4 3	1.41
15. Before I behave aggressively, anything makes me lose my temper	.791*	.626	1.3 9	1.66

* $p < .001$.

Table 4. Internal Consistency of the CAIE Total Scale and Subscales

	α	ω	M	SD
Scale I (11 items)	.86	.8	11.59	9.82
		6		
Scale E (11 items)	.89	.9	15.21	11.83
		0		
CAIE Total (22 items)	.92	.9	26.81	20.16
		3		

Note. Scale I = Instrumental Scale; Scale E = Expressive Scale; CAIE = Instrumental and Expressive Aggression Questionnaire.

Table 5 . Correlations between the CAIE and other Violence Risk Instruments

	PCL-R Factor 1	PCL-R Factor 2	PCL-R total score	VRAG total score	SAQ total score
Scale I	.25*	.47*	.42*	.38*	.44*
Scale E	.27*	.51*	.46*	.39*	.55*
CAIE total	.28*	.53*	.48*	.42*	.53*

Note. Scale I = Instrumental Scale; Scale E = Expressive Scale; CAIE = Instrumental and Expressive Aggression Questionnaire; PCL-R = Psychopathy Checklist-Revised; VRAG = Violence Risk Appraisal Guide; SAQ = Self-Appraisal Questionnaire; PCL-R Factor 1 = Interpersonal/Affective; PCL-R Factor 2 = Lifestyle/Antisocial.

* $p < .01$.

Table 6. Means, Standard Deviations, t-Values, and Effect Sizes of the CAIE for Institutional Infractions and non-infractions

	Infractions (<i>n</i> = 130)		Non-Infractions (<i>n</i> = 172)		Student' <i>s t</i>	η_p^2
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
Scale I	15.03	9.12	9.00	9.55	-5.53**	.093
Scale E	19.68	11.97	11.83	10.57	-6.03**	.108
CAIE total	34.71	20.27	20.83	17.95	-6.28**	.116

Note. Scale I = Instrumental Scale; Scale E = Expressive Scale; CAIE = Instrumental and Expressive Aggression Questionnaire.

** $p < .05$.

Figure 1. ROC curve for CAIE total score, subscales, and recidivism
Note. CAIE = Instrumental and Expressive Aggression Questionnaire

Figure 2. ROC curve comparisons for CAIE total score, CAIE subscales, PCL-R, PCL-R Factors, and recidivism

Note. CAIE = Instrumental and Expressive Aggression Questionnaire; PCL-R = Psychopathy Checklist-Revised; PCL-R Factor 1 = Interpersonal/Affective; PCL-R Factor 2 = Lifestyle/Antisocial.